

Kinetics of Oxidation of Substituted Benzaldehydes by Acid Bromate

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The kinetics of oxidation of benzaldehyde and some substituted benzaldehydes (*o*-Cl, *m*-Cl, *p*-Cl, *o*-F, *m*-F and *p*-F) have been investigated in aqueous acetic acid medium in the presence of sulphuric acid. The reaction exhibits first order both in substrate and oxidant, and second order in hydrogen ion. The reaction at constant excess $[H^+]$ follows the rate expression,

$$-\frac{d[Br(V)]}{dt} = k [Br(V)] [aldehyde].$$

The rate of the reaction increases with increasing acetic acid content of the medium. The order of reactivity of substituted benzaldehyde is,

$m\text{-Cl} > m\text{-F} > o\text{-Cl} > p\text{-Cl} > o\text{-F} > H > p\text{-F}$.

the rho value is +1.1. A mechanism involving rate-determining formation of a bromate ester which decomposes to products in a fast step has been proposed.

POTASSIUM bromate is being increasingly used as an oxidant for several classes of organic compounds. Secondary alcohols¹, cyclanols^{2,3}, phenols⁴, α -hydroxy acids⁵ and aliphatic aldehydes^{6,7} were found to be smoothly oxidised by this reagent. We report in this paper the kinetics of oxidation of some benzaldehydes in acid medium with this oxidant.

Experimental

All chemicals used were of A.R. grade. The reactions were carried out in binary solvent mixtures of acetic acid and water. To avoid the formation of bromine, all the experiments were carried out in the presence of mercuric acetate. The rate of reaction was followed by withdrawing aliquots of the reaction mixture at different intervals of time and quenching in potassium iodide solution. The liberated iodine was titrated against standardised sodium thiosulphate solution using starch as indicator. The pseudo first order rate coefficients were obtained by plotting $\log(a-x)$ values against time⁸.

Results and Discussion

Effect of oxidant concentration: The rate coefficients are independent of the initial concentration of bromate, indicating that the reaction is first order in bromate (Table 1).

Effect of substrate concentration: A plot of $\log k_1$ (Table 1) against $\log [aldehyde]$ was linear with a slope of one, for each substituted aldehyde studied. The k_1 values on division by the corresponding aldehyde concentration gave a constant value within the experimental error. The data in Table 1 substantiate that the reaction is first order in substrate also.

Effect of $[H^+]$: Reactions were carried out by changing the sulphuric acid concentration in the reaction medium. The values of pseudo first order rate constant, k_1 increased with the increase in sulphuric acid concentration indicating the involvement of the acid at some stage or other. At 0.50, 0.75, 1.00, 1.25, 1.50 and 1.75 *M* sulphuric acid, the $10^5 k_1$ values of 2.28, 4.06, 6.54, 10.4, 13.5 and 19.9 sec^{-1} , respectively have been obtained. A plot of $\log k_1$ vs $\log [H^+]$ is linear with a slope of two. This proves that the reaction is second order in hydrogen ion concentration.

Effect of solvent composition: The reaction rate increases with increasing acetic acid content in the medium (Table 2). Decreasing dielectric constant of the medium favours the reaction indicating that the reaction is of ion-dipole type⁹.

Effect of mercuric acetate: To ascertain that there is no interaction between mercuric ions and benzaldehyde, a few sets were carried out by varying the concentration of mercuric acetate¹⁰. The k_1 values are constant. This proves that the mercuric

TABLE 1—EFFECT OF VARYING [BROMATE] AND [ALDEHYDE] CONCENTRATION ON RATE OF OXIDATION AT 35°

[Hg(OAc)₂] = 2.0 × 10⁻³ M, Solvent : 50% HOAc-50% H₂O (v/v) [H₂SO₄] = 0.5 M

Variation of [aldehyde] [Bromate] : 1.0 × 10 ⁻³ M			Variation of [bromate] [Aldehyde] : 2.5 × 10 ⁻³ M		
10 ³ k ₁ /S dm ³ mol ⁻¹ sec ⁻¹	10 ⁴ k ₁ sec ⁻¹	10 ² [Aldehyde] × 10 ³ M	Substituent	10 ³ [Bromate] M	10 ⁴ k ₁ sec ⁻¹
0.916	1.84	2.0	H	1.00	2.25*
0.913	2.28	2.5		2.00	2.19*
0.900	2.70	3.0		3.00	2.11*
0.900	3.60	4.0		4.21	2.12*
2.78	5.55	2.0	<i>o</i> -Cl	1.00	6.76
2.70	6.76	2.5		2.00	6.99
2.40	7.19	3.0		3.00	7.13
2.70	10.8	4.0		4.00	6.87
2.56	12.8	5.0		5.00	6.76
4.56	11.4	2.5	<i>m</i> -Cl	1.00	11.4
4.55	13.7	3.0		2.00	10.9
4.49	17.9	4.0		3.00	11.2
				4.00	10.0
1.96	4.90	2.5	<i>p</i> -Cl	1.00	4.90
1.87	5.61	3.0		2.00	4.80
2.03	7.11	3.5		3.00	4.69
2.00	8.00	4.0		4.00	4.80
1.93	4.88	2.5	<i>o</i> -F	1.00	4.88
2.06	6.17	3.0		2.00	4.80
1.98	6.95	3.5		3.00	4.81
1.94	7.76	4.0			
4.00	10.0	2.5	<i>m</i> -F	1.00	10.0
4.00	11.9	3.0		3.00	10.1
3.89	13.6	3.5		4.00	9.91
3.98	15.9	4.0		5.00	10.0
1.37	2.75	2.0	<i>p</i> -F	1.00	3.07
1.23	3.07	2.5		2.00	3.04
1.35	4.04	3.0		3.00	3.01
1.32	5.27	4.0			

* Temperature = 30°

TABLE 2—EFFECT OF SOLVENT COMPOSITION ON RATE OF OXIDATION AT 35°

[Aldehyde] = 2.5 × 10⁻³ M, [Hg(OAc)₂] = 2.0 × 10⁻³ M,
[Bromate] = 1.0 × 10⁻³ M, [H₂SO₄] = 0.5 M

Substituent	k ₁ × 10 ³ dm ³ mol ⁻¹ sec ⁻¹				
	% Acetic acid				
	30	40	50	60	70
H	0.44	0.60	0.91	2.20	4.48
	0.89	1.27	1.84	3.20	9.20
<i>o</i> -Cl	1.11	1.64	2.70	6.20	11.00
<i>m</i> -Cl	1.61	2.53	4.56	8.51	20.7
<i>p</i> -Cl	—	1.28	1.96	3.90	10.2
<i>o</i> -F	0.90	1.22	1.93	3.46	9.60
<i>m</i> -F	1.27	2.46	4.00	8.28	20.6
<i>p</i> -F	—	—	1.23	2.40	7.16

* Temperature = 30°

acetate did not influence the reaction in any way other than 'fixing' Br⁻, thereby, avoiding the oxidation of the latter to molecular bromine.

Effect of salt: Different concentrations of sodium nitrate, potassium nitrate and potassium sulphate did not alter the rate constant, giving additional evidence for ion-dipole type of reaction.

Effect of temperature: Experiments have been carried out at 35, 40, 45 and 50° under identical con-

centration of reagents (Table 3). The plots of log k₁ vs 1/T are linear. The activation parameters are reported in Table 3.

Structural effect: The reaction is facilitated by electron-withdrawing substituents. The order of reactivity at 35° is,

The *p*-fluorobenzaldehyde is less reactive than benzaldehyde itself, which may be due to the +M effect of fluorine. Since there is direct conjugation between the *para*-fluoro group and the electron-withdrawing aldehyde group, electron density can be transferred from the fluorine to the aldehyde group. Consequent to this +M effect becoming predominant over the -I effect, the electron density at the carbonyl group would be greater in *p*-fluorobenzaldehyde than in benzaldehyde. This would reduce the reactivity of the *para*-fluoro compound.

The Hammett plot (Fig. 1) is linear though the points corresponding to *para*-chloro and *para*-fluoro compounds do not fit well. However, when the σ⁺ values instead of σ values are used for these substituents the points fitted well on the linear Hammett plot, confirming the influence of +M effect.

TABLE 3—EFFECT OF TEMPERATURE AND ACTIVATION PARAMETERS FOR OXIDATION OF BENZALDEHYDES BY ACID BROMATE IN 50% ACETIC ACID

[Bromate] = 1.0×10^{-3} M,
[Aldehyde] = 2.5×10^{-3} M,

[Hg(OAc)₂] = 2.0×10^{-3} M
[H₂SO₄] = 0.500 M

Substituent	$k_2, \times 10^3 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$					E_a	$\Delta H^\ddagger$	$\Delta G^\ddagger$	$-\Delta S^\ddagger$
	30.0	35.0	40.0	45.0	50.0				
H	0.911	1.84	2.88	4.64	—	85.6	88.0	91.7	28.3
o-Cl	—	2.70	4.87	8.71	11.8	83.0	80.5	90.7	33.3
m-Cl	—	4.66	7.32	11.0	17.6	78.7	71.1	89.4	59.8
p-Cl	—	1.96	3.22	5.24	8.16	78.8	76.2	91.6	49.9
o-F	1.11	1.98	2.98	4.82	—	78.0	75.5	91.6	52.4
m-F	2.83	4.00	6.60	10.9	—	73.0	70.4	89.7	62.7
p-F	—	1.23	2.67	3.64	6.35	86.7	84.2	92.2	26.0

E_a , $\Delta H^\ddagger$ and $\Delta G^\ddagger$ in kJ mol^{-1} , and $\Delta S^\ddagger$ in $\text{J mol}^{-1} \text{ K}^{-1}$.

Fig. 1. Hammett plot.

Mechanism: The data favour a reaction involving free aldehyde molecule and H₂Br⁺O₃. The aldehyde forms an ester with H₂Br⁺O₃ which undergoes intramolecular electron transfer leading to the formation of product. The formation of the bromate ester by the attack of the oxidant species at the substrate is assumed to be the rate determining step.

In the transition state a dispersal of charges is likely due to the formation of a six-membered cyclic system. Hence, relative to the reactants the transition state would be solvated more in a media of low dielectric constant. Accordingly, increasing acetic acid content increases the ease of reaction which lends additional support to the mechanism.

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